

PHILOSOPHICAL KNOWLEDGE AS A FACTOR LEADING MAN TO TRUTH AND GOODNESS

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The article reveals thoughts about the science of philosophy, philosophical knowledge, truth, goodness, and spiritual perfection. Philosophical knowledge, theory of knowledge, and knowledge related to logical methods are also mentioned.

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Knowledge is a step of spiritual ascension for the perfection of human life, food for thought, and the basis of worldview. A person's knowledge distinguishes him from an animal, and language started his outward and inward socialization. Philosophical knowledge becomes even more important in the current era, when the level of knowledge of a person has increased and the possibilities of knowledge have expanded. Because philosophical knowledge is a factor that brings general, special and professional knowledge closer together and systematizes. Because even a person who is tired of philosophical lessons, debates and arguments relies on philosophical knowledge without realizing it.

Educated and highly spiritual people are interested in philosophical knowledge. Philosophical knowledge is therefore necessary for all professionals and is taught at higher levels of education.

Humanity cannot turn away from its many thousand-year-old values, just as the science of history cannot abandon the past. After all, the values that eras, policies, and kingdoms could not destroy and cannot destroy still show their necessity, without them humanity seems to have lost its mind and understanding.

Philosophy likes versatility, multifacetedness, multifacetedness. Philosophy is not opposed to the diversity of understanding and understanding in relation to an object or phenomenon. Different people interpret life differently. Because people have different levels, inner worlds, and knowledge. Deep thinking is realized with deep knowledge, clear thinking, sharp observation. Philosophy is like an ocean, a person who dives into it can bring out either a pearl or an unnecessary, worthless stone. Someone who prioritizes logical thinking is an innovator, and if not, doesn't have anything fancy.

Is there a coincidence in science? Yes, but chance does not work where there is no effort. One of the Western scientists said that chance can only help a well-prepared mind. If we cannot think with absolute precision, the devil will play us." [2.126]

The formation of philosophical knowledge is an internal act that ignites other arguments. Because of this action, the thinking machine, which requires intellectual courage, is started and a scientific landscape is created from the facts coming from outside. For this reason, a unified and revolving worldview can only be achieved through teaching (with lectures and seminars). But it's clear that in the process of teaching, you spill some author's

point of view on the listener. A broad-minded philosopher who makes logical conclusions and draws his conclusions based on rich life material cannot be prepared only by teaching in lectures and seminars or by informing about philosophy in other ways. A philosopher is born in the exercises of debate and deep thinking.

Every field of science has an ideological rock, a foundation. Such a basis of philosophy is truth or the secrets of all worlds. Strange ideas and unfounded views are always hidden behind philosophy.

When the time comes, it is worth noting that every person who claims to be a philosopher should have his own say in this world. Quoting from the words of others is useful in the educational process to prove one or another point, but in scientific activity, conclusions and judgments must be made by the author. Jalaluddin Rumi said to those who were sitting in a meeting with his friend Shamsiddin Tabrizi, "When will you say the words that are yours in their original essence?" [3.112] appealed.

Those who cover other people's words are like a singer who imitates other people's songs. If the factor that makes the human body healthy is sport, work, and the environment, the factors that make his spirituality healthy are a healthy idea or philosophical knowledge that builds it. If a person puts a lot of emphasis on other knowledge and objects or doubts it, it should be noted that the criterion of truth in all knowledge or its weight is created by philosophical knowledge and philosophical thinking. The master of everyday knowledge means his teacher and the thinkers of the past. Philosophy does not compare the word teacher only to people, but also includes God, nature, and life among its teachers.

A creator, a philosopher, who tells stories about his past, but is ignorant of the spiritual world of people, is like a robber caught in the intoxication of sophistication. Today it is there, and tomorrow it is not!

In the field of art and philosophy, there are very few stars, and there are a lot of sunflowers that appear today and fade away tomorrow. Talented creators in the mass media may not be able to get their turn from the next generation. Talent shows itself as if a piece of gold shines from a pile of garbage.

Philosophical knowledge is always valuable knowledge. It is a system of views focused on the world, a person, a world of comprehensible conclusions. Every era puts a series of questions to its philosophers and waits for their answers. The universal source of all our knowledge is human experience. Philosophical knowledge is ultimately demonstrated by analysis and observations. Before death comes, every person should have his own saying. If a person's presence or absence is unimportant for the neighborhood and society, know that he is living as an individual.

Life experience, observation helps to understand the "what" of the phenomenon. Philosophy begins with understanding the reason why it is so. With the formula of understanding the world - thinking - causation, a person approaches active philosophy.

The scope of discussion of philosophy is so wide that it is easier to answer the question of what is not philosophy than what is philosophy. Because it is more difficult to answer the question "why is it like that" than the question "what is it".

If medicine is an activity aimed at solving problems of the body, philosophy deals with the human spirit and spirituality, worldview. This means that you cannot blindly apply medicine to spirituality or vice versa.

If the truth was the main basis for a philosopher, I would consider a person who can prove that two times two are four and not four, a real philosopher. This requires encyclopedic knowledge and the art of persuasion

In the word "I" of philosophy, the originality, uniqueness, identity of a person is hidden. The ego is the person's individuality. When a person chooses a path that goes against the interests of others for his own personal benefit, it leads to egoism. Egoism is a lack of self-love. The place of doubt in science is incomparable, but it is wrong to be suspicious of scientists. Before rejecting the dubious information, unproven conclusion that has reached you, take comfort in your heart, listen to it: is its solution beneficial to science, people and yourself? If not, don't waste your time.

It is better for a student to follow his teacher at the beginning, but he should have his own way in creativity and scientific activity. Not being able to get his own way is a sign of immaturity, and imitation becomes his hobby. Just as there are imitators, there are also imitators.

Also, nature, society, man himself are great teachers given to us by God. We grow up by learning from them. That's why at one time His Holiness Jalaluddin Rumi said: "Hey bud! Teach me to express myself!" [1.208] ¹ had pleaded. So, we are surrounded by a large number of teachers, they are kind and generous. It is up to us to receive their training and knowledge or not. As long as knowledge is the basis of human perfection, if a person rising towards perfection does not benefit people, the knowledge he has acquired is meaningless, he is selfish. After all, human perfection is the stairs of society's interest.

The goal is people, the goal is the benefit of society! Conditions and country peace are necessary for the development of philosophy. The Roman philosopher Seneca, who lived at the beginning of Christ, wrote in one of his letters: "The more valuable a traveler's luggage is, the more he cares about the tranquility of the sea. The god is grateful to Neptune for the calmness of the water. A philosopher also needs the peace of the country, he always expresses gratitude to the creators of peace"² he writes. The wealth of our country is peace and youth. Our people, who hope for youth, live in deep gratitude to the head of the country, who is the creator of the peace of our country. It is true that one of the locomotives of our development is peace and the right path. Seneca developed his opinion and wrote: "Philosophy does not like instability and dissociation of words and practice"[1.161].

If we compare the situation in our country with neighboring countries, it becomes clear how correct this opinion is, how lucky it is to be a child and a citizen of this country.

A person who has passed away is remembered by his colleagues, if he is a scientist, by the scientists of his field. People will benefit from the spiritual and material heritage left behind. A person who is alive in death is greater than the one who is dead in life. The greatness of the scientist's scientific heritage is a sign of his aliveness.

¹ 96 mumtoz faylasuf. – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2011.

² 96 mumtoz faylasuf. – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2011.

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